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Influences of *Moringa oleifera* seed on *Corcyra cephalonica*: A Moth damaging rice Lepidopterans : Pyralidae

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ABSTRACT

In the storage of rice grains, damage by insect pests is a severe problem. *Moringa oleifera* has insecticidal properties against a wide variety of insect pests, moths, and beetles. It can be grown mainly in tropical countries and its growth is rapid as compared to other trees. All the parts of this plant have been used for its medicinal value, but this study is taken to see the effect of dry powder seeds of *Moringa oleifera* for its insecticidal properties on larval mortality and the emergence of the *Corcyra cephalonica* in the storage of rice (*Oryza sativa*). 1, 2, 3, and 4 grams of seed powder were used against the *Corcyra cephalonica* on 50 gm rice packed in gunny sample bags for the period of 120 days (4 months) by dusty treatment. Treatment was found very effective on 8 day, its insecticidal property increases with an increase in concentration. Treatment using 1, 2, 3, and 4 grams of seed powder on the 8th day shows larval mortality 57%, 66%, 77%, and 83%, respectively in increasing order.

KEYWORDS: *Moringa oleifera*, emergence, mortality, dusty treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Moringa oleifera is commonly known as a drumstick tree and is grown in various tropical countries, also native to India. The Indian people have been using all the parts of *Moringa* plants for curing various ailments since ancient times. Now a days *Moringa* plant is gaining importance as a pest-controlling insecticide due to its fewer side effects and low cost. Previous research confirmed the presence of lectin in *Moringa* seeds, which has deleterious effects on different stages of the lepidopterans.

Rice is the most important tropical cereal and supplies about a quarter of the entire calorie intake of humans. Rice is the staple food of many people more than any other food grain and is 90 percent grown and consumed in South and Southeast Asia, which are major centers of the world population.

Rice (*Oryza sativa*) starchy cereal grain belongs to the genus *Oryza* and there are two main cultigens: *O. sativa* in Asia and *O. glaberrima* in Africa (Cating David 1992). It is a semi-aquatic gramineous crop of great diversity. Unfortunately, rice is infested by many insect pests during storage. *Corcyra cephalonica* is one of these pests. Presently highly toxic chemicals are used by

farmers against storage insect pests. These toxic chemical pesticides cause severe problems to the environment and human health.

Herbal insecticides are the utmost need of the present time in place of toxic chemicals due to their broad-spectrum insecticidal properties and low cost. Seeds of *Moringa oleifera* have insecticidal properties against a wide range of rice storage insects.

The rice moth, *Corcyra cephalonica*, is a Lepidopterous pest of stored grains . It is widely spread and causes severe damage to rice during storage under different environmental conditions. This insect pest has been widely reported from continents such as Europe, Asia, Africa, and North America (Jhala et al., 2019) while it is still spreading to other regions of the world via the transportation of infested grains and commodities (Samodra and Ibrahim, 2006).

The larval stage is very destructive infesting damaged or broken cereal grains. Feeding continues till the whole grain is destroyed and the shell is broken into silken fibers, which become dense with time converting the contaminated products into lumps (Samodra and Ibrahim, 2006). Infected with larval feces, webbings, exuviae, and remains of dead moths reduces human acceptance and, the market value of the products.

Moringa oleifera can be grown easily and its growth is rapid as compared to other trees. Trees of *Moringa oleifera* are widely distributed in India. So, we tried to find its effectiveness against *Corcyra cephalonica* on the rice *Oryza sativa*. Powder of dried seeds of *Moringa oleifera* is used in this research work.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Rice was procured from the local grain dealer and cleaned properly with the mesh. The quality was tested and confirmed with the help of some agriculturists. There was no sign of infestation on the grains.

Seeds of the *Moringa* were collected from the roadside of Shukla Ganj, Unnao in the month of March of the year 2021. After thorough cleaning seeds were dried and finely powdered and spread on the 50gm bags of rice. Sample bags were treated with four concentrations i.e. 1g, 2g, 3g, and 4g dose of *Moringa oleifera* seed powder. In the case of control, seeds were treated only with distilled water. Then individuals were allowed to feed the treated grains.

All the experiments were performed under laboratory conditions at temperatures $28 \pm 2^{\circ}$ C and relative humidity $75 \pm 5\%$ for 120 days in the Department of Zoology and Chemistry at PPN College, Kanpur.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Research shows that the seed of *Moringa oleifera* has insecticidal properties without any side effects on human beings. Observation shows that with 1 gm treatment of seed powder, there was no mortality on the 2nd day, but on the 3rd it was found 9% and increased by 62% mortality on the 8th day. Where as 2gm dose treatment shows 17% and 18% on the 2nd and the 3rd day, larval

mortality increases on the 4th day and 5th day, 28% to 34%. But on the 6th and 7th day, 42% to 57% and but it abruptly increases to about 68% on the 8th day. 3gms concentration brought on 26%, 36%, 42%, 46%, 52%, 65%, and 72% mortality on the 2nd day, 3rd day, 4th day, 5th day, 6th day, 7th day, and 8th day, respectively. In 4 gms, exposure caused higher killing. On the 2nd day, there was 39% and on the 3rd day, 53% mortality was observed 59% on the 4th day, 63% on the 5th day, 69% on the 6th day, and 71% mortality was noticed on the 7th day of observation. 10% mortality was added on the 8th day i.e. 83%. The control did not show any mortality till the fourth day but on the 5th day, only 8% larvae were found dead. registered, a total of 29% mortality was noted in control.

A similar result was found by Kawakib Awadh Atshan, et al (2017), when studying the “Effect of seed Extracts as insecticides against Lepidopteran Pests on cauliflower”, Dhananjay Kumar Tiwari, Anu Bhardwaj, et.al saw the ‘Pesticidal activities in five medicinal plants collected from mid hills of western Himalayas’ in industrial Crops and products (2005), Sileshi Degu, Asfaw Berihun, et.Al. ‘Medicinal Plants that are used as a repellent, insecticide, and larvicide in Ethiopia’ Pharmacy and Pharmacology (2017), Roger Ducos Fokou Youmsi, Patrick (2017) Ethnobotanical Survey of “medicinal plants used as insect repellents” in six malaria-endemic localities of Cameroon. Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine., Prof. T.V. Sathe, Dr. Dattatray, et al “Sucking insect pests and medicinal value of Tulsi *Ocimum sanctum* L. (Lamiaceae)”. Indian Journal of Applied Science (2014), Lopamudra Sethi and Preetha Bhadra (2020), Kumari and Kumar (2001), Kumari Punam, Bidhu Sahay Singh and Dhyanendra Kumar (2004), Khatre V.M., Kachora BV. & Mote UN (1993), Pandey Alok Kumar and SP. Srivastava (2007), Pandey Alok Kumar and S.P. Srivastava (2007) A review paper on Tulsi Plant, International Bimonthly., Pandey, N.D, Singh Shiv Raj and Tiwari G.C.: (1976), Pandey Harishankar (1995), Pandey S.C. (1995) “Effect of neem leaf powder on survival and mortality of pulse-beetle *Callosobruchus chinensis* (L) infesting black gram”;; Srivastava K.P., 2002.

Table : 1 Effect of *Moringa oleifera* powder on *Corcyra cephalonica* (Rice moth)

Doses		Durations						
		2 nd Day	3 rd Day	4 th Day	5 th Day	6 th Day	7 th Day	8 th Day
1gm	M	-	9%	18%	21%	32%	47%	62%
2gm	M	17%	18%	28%	34%	42%	57%	68%
3 gm	M	26%	36%	42%	46%	52%	65%	72%
4 gm	M	39%	53%	59%	63%	69%	71%	83%
Control	M				8%			29%

Graph No.-1 Effect of *Moringa oleifera* powder on *Corcyra cephalonica* (Rice moth).

NOTE: Fig in Parentheses and Transformed Value. M=Mortality

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